

Synthesis of 3-[α -(3-Chloro-2-oxo-4-substituted-phenyl/furfuryl-1-azetidiny)]-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones and 3-[α -(2-Substituted-phenyl/furfurylthiazolidiznyl)]-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones as C.N.S. -active Agents

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Reaction of 3-substituted-phenylidene/furfurylidineamino-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones (3*a*-*d*) with chloroacetyl chloride and thioglycolic acid affords the corresponding four-membered azetidiones (4*a*-*d*) and five-membered thiazolidinones (5*a*-*d*) respectively. All the compounds were tested for their acute toxicity, effects on gross behaviour, spontaneous motor activity (SMA), anorexigenic activity, neuroleptic activity and anticonvulsant activity. Compounds 4*a* and 5*d* exhibited C.N.S. depressant activity.

Benzopyran-2-ones exhibit significant biological activities¹. In continuation of our work on possible C.N.S. -active compounds, attempts were made to synthesise benzopyran-2-one derivatives incorporating four-membered azetidiones and five-membered thiazolidinones which are known to be pharmacophoric in nature² at position-3. All the compounds were evaluated for their acute toxicity and gross behavioural effects.

The starting compound 3-amino-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-one (1) was synthesised by minor modification of a known procedure³ by cyclisation of salicylaldehyde with *N*-acetylglycine in acetic anhydride with trace amount of piperidine and subsequent deacetylation with concentrated HCl in EtOH resulted compound 2. Condensation of 2 with aromatic aldehydes in EtOH containing trace amount of glacial acetic acid gave 3-substitutedphenyladine-/furfurylidineamino-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones (3*a*-*d*), which were converted into the azetidiones (4*a*-*d*) and the thiazolidinones (5*a*-*d*) by reaction with chloroacetyl chloride and thioglycolic acid respectively (Scheme 1).

Biological activity : All the compounds were

Scheme 1

evaluated for acute toxicity and gross behavioural effects⁴. ALD₅₀ of the compounds was found to be high : 4*a*-*d*, 5*a*, 681; 5*b*, 825; 5*c,d*, 1000 mg/kg

ip. At 1/5th of the ALD₅₀ these compounds exhibited no significant gross behavioural effects except compounds **4a** and **5d** which exhibited C.N.S. depressant activity in both gross behavioural studies (qualitative) as well as in their effect on spontaneous motor activity measured by using an acto photometer. None of the compounds however exhibited any significant anticonvulsant and anorexigenic activities in mice or neuroleptic activity in rats, at dose levels, which produced no fallout in rota rod test.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-360L spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

3-Amino-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (1) : A mixture of salicylaldehyde (0.15 mol) and *N*-acetylglycine (0.1 mol) in acetic anhydride (20.4 ml) with a trace of piperidine was heated in an oil-bath at 130–34° for 6 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water (10 ml) and further refluxed for 1 h. Then excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from EtOH, (82%), m.p. 205–06°; ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 1 710 (δ -lactone), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (CONH).

To a solution of **1** (0.1 mol) in EtOH (61 ml) was added concentrated HCl (20 ml) dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled, diluted with water and neutralised with aq. NaHCO₃ (10%). The solid thus separated was washed with water and crystallised from EtOH to yield **2** (80%), m.p. 130–31°; ν_{\max} 3 420, 3 300, 3 300 (NH₂), 1 710 (δ -lactone), 1 640 (=NH bend), 1 330 cm⁻¹ (C–N).

3-Substituted-phenyldine/furfurylidineamino-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones (3a–d) : A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol) and an appropriate aromatic aldehyde (0.015 mol) in absolute EtOH (30 ml) in presence of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 8 h. Then solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid thus obtained was washed with EtOAc-hexane mixture (1 : 1), then with cold water and crystallised from

MeOH (yields 68–85%) (Table 1) : **3a** ν_{\max} 1 710 (δ -lactone), 1 690 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3–5*

Compd.	Ar	M p.°C
3a	C ₆ H ₅	140–50
b	C ₄ H ₃ O	195–200
c	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	185–95
d	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	120–25
4a	C ₆ H ₅	180–85
b	C ₄ H ₃ O	165–70
c	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	205–15
d	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	180–90
5a	C ₆ H ₅	245–48
b	C ₄ H ₃ O	200–10
c	2-OH.C ₆ H ₅	280–85
d	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	222–225

*Nitrogen analysis was found satisfactory.

3-[α -(3-Chloro-2-oxo-4-substituted-phenylfurfuryl-1-azetidiny)]-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones (4a–d) : To **3a–d** (0.01 mol) in dioxane (50 ml) were added chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) and Et₃N (0.1 mol) at 0° with stirring. The mixture was left at room temperature for 3 h, then refluxed for 10 h, excess of solvent distilled off and the residue was poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent (Table 1) : **4a** ν_{\max} 3 310 (CH), 1 720 (δ -lactone), 1 680 (cyclic C=O lactone), 740 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl); δ 4.45–4.6 (1H, d, N–CH), 6.95–7.1 (1H, d, CH–Cl), 7.25 (1H, s, C=CH), 7.35–7.75 (9H, m, ArH); *m/z* 325 (*M*⁺, 10%), 249 (*M*⁺–C₆H₅, 15%), 221 (13.7%), 161 (*B*⁺, aminobenzopyran-2-one ion 100%, base peak), 133 (*B*⁺–C⁺ = 0, 3.2%), 77 (30%).

3-[α -(2-Substituted-phenylfurfurylthiazolidinyl)]-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones (5a–d) : To **3a–d** (0.01 mol) in DMF (30 ml) were added thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) and ZnCl₂ (in traces). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h, then cooled and poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was crystallised from DMF/water (Table 1) : **5a** ν_{\max} 2 850 (CH), 1 720 (δ -lactone) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (C–N); δ 3.6–3.75 (2H, s, CO–CH₂–S), 5.7 (1H, s, N–CH, thiazolidinone ring), 7.25 (1H, s, C=CH), 7.35–7.75 (9H, m, ArH); *m/z* 323 [*M*⁺, 12%], 233 [*M*⁺–HC⁺–C₆H₅, 34.3%], 161 (*B*⁺ aminobenzopyranone ion, 100% base peak), 145 (benzopyranone ion, 51%), 132 (*B*⁺–C⁺ = 0.11%), 77 (C₆H₅, 20%).

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